

Sylva Lacinová's reliefs from the ceremonial hall Brno – Královo Pole

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Two wooden reliefs called *Dvojice* (in English *Pair*) are on the walls at the entrance to the ceremonial hall in Brno–Králové Pole, the Czech Republic. One is to the right, and the other to the left of the entrance. They are the work of the Brno sculptor Sylva Lacinová (1923–2019) and were made in connection with the reconstruction of the hall in the late 1960s.

The whole set is a tender reminder of partner life. To the left is a relief depicting two human figures merging. It is about lovers and their love and the feelings that connect them. Their life story continues in true relief. After getting married in the ceremony hall, they become a family. Therefore, the right relief shows a third, small figure, their descendant.

Both works are conceived slightly abstractly – their proportions are shown schematically in the surface masses. This style of representation has been typical for Sylva Lacinová since the 1960s, when, thanks to the loosening of the austere social climate, artists' expressions in works of art also became looser. This is one of Sylva Lacinová's most famous expressive concepts. In it, the artist may be following the early 20th-century works of Vincent Makovský, her teacher from the School of Art in Zlín, or the British sculptor Henry Moore, whose studio she visited in the 1960s.